

were planted in each pot. BR3 is susceptible to Zn deficiency and ufra disease caused by the stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* (Butler) Filipjev. Pots were irrigated with pond water with no Zn contamination. Symptoms of Zn deficiency in plants grown in pots without added Zn were observed 20 d after planting.

Plants from 4 pots of each group (with and without added Zn) were inoculated with 200 ufra nematodes/plant, 25 and 35 d after planting, by seedling base and sheath inoculation methods. Immediately after inoculation, the plants were covered with polyethylene bags for 72 h to increase humidity. Soil in the pots was always submerged.

Splash-patterned chlorosis developed 2 to 4 wk after inoculation, followed by

Zn content of plant and soil, and its effect on stem nematode-infected rice plants, BRRI.^a

Treatment ^b	Zn content (ppm)			Fertile tillers (%)	UI (%)	UII (%)	Filled grains per panicle (%)	Av yield (g/pot)	Nematode multiplication rate at panicle initiation
	In soil		In plant at harvest						
	Initial	Final							
Without added Zn	0.6	0.5	25.3	15.1	75.7	24.3	8.8	0.7	1:14
With added Zn	0.6	3.8	39.3	28.5	62.6	37.4	30.0	2.1	1:12
't' value ^c			9.2**	2.6*	3.9**	3.9**	4.1**	2.5*	0.3 ns

^aFigures are av of 4 replications. ^bZn was added as ZnSO₄ (50 ppm) at transplanting and the plants were inoculated with nematode, at 25 and 35 d after transplanting, by seedling base and sheath inoculation methods. ^c** = 1% level of significance, * = 5% level of significance, ns = not significant.

other ufra symptoms such as yellowing and twisting and crinkling of younger leaves. There were two different patterns of panicle emergence: panicles fully enclosed within the flag leaf sheath (UI), and partially emerged panicles with a few

filled grains at the tip (UII).

Zn-deficient plants had less fertile tillers, fewer filled grains, and more severe ufra symptoms than plants with added Zn (see table). □

Incidence of rice root nematode in Madurai

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The rice root nematode *Hirschmanniella* sp. significantly reduces rice growth and yield in India. We surveyed 33 blocks of Madurai district for rice root nematode incidence in 1981-82 and 1982-83.

IR20 and Ponni are the rice varieties grown in the area in samba. Root samples were collected from active tillering phase to heading from eight randomly selected fields from four villages per block. Ten 5-g root samples were taken from randomly selected clumps in each field and processed by the Baermann funnel technique. The population of rice root nematodes *H. oryzae* and *H. mucronata* was recorded. Damage level was considered to be more than 250 nematodes/5-g root.

Rice root nematode was found in all areas surveyed. Populations ranged from 49 to 521 nematodes/5 g of root. Infestation was most severe in Cumbum tract of the Periyar Irrigation Project, and popula-

tion was above damage level in Alanganaloor, Bodi, Chinnamanoor, Cumbum, Dindigul, Palani, Periyakulam, Sanarpatti, Theni, Usilampatti, and Uthamapalayam. □

TKM9 is resistant to rice-root nematode

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IR20, IR50, Paiyur 1, and TKM9 were evaluated at different growth stages for resistance to rice-root nematode *Hirschmanniella oryzae*.

TKM9 was resistant to nematodes at all growth stages (see table). IR50 was more resistant than IR20 and Paiyur 1.

Rice varietal resistance to rice root nematode, Kancheepuram, India.

Variety	Nematode population in 2 g of root			
	Planting	30 d after transplanting	Boot leaf	Harvest
IR20	5	20	50	35
IR50	5	—	5	25
Palyur 1	30	240	10	10
TKM9	—	—	—	—

Insecticide root dip controls rice root nematode

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We evaluated insecticide root dips for control of rice root nematode *Hirschmanniella oryzae* during navarai season.

IR50 seedlings were dipped in 0.02% solutions of phosphamidon, chlorpyrifos, or monocrotophos for 20 min before planting.

Phosphamidon and chlorpyrifos root dips reduced the nematode population 30 d after transplanting (see table). □

Insecticide root dips evaluated for rice root nematode control at Kancheepuram, India.

Insecticide (0.02% solution)	Nematodes/2 g root
Phosphamidon	0.83
Chlorpyrifos	0.83
Monocrotophos	1.66
No treatment	5.83

SE = 0.34